

Flux/Flow Equations and Momentum as $p=Ev$ Versus $v=E/p$ Part II

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In Part I we argued that two flow equations for a free particle, namely: d/dx (partial) $A(x,t) = p$ ((1a)) and d/dt (partial) $A(x,t) = -E$ ((1a)) may be applied to both particles with rest mass and those without. In fact we argue that there are at least three scenarios associated with ((1a)) and ((1b)). The first is classical mechanics for a particle with rest mass m_0 and constant velocity. Using ((1a)) and ((1b)) with $p=E(v)v$ this scenario yields special relativity. A second solution is to write ((1a)) and ((1b)) as eigenvalue equations: $-id/dx$ (partial) $\exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and id/dt (partial) $\exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$ where $A=-Et+px$. This yields a quantum mechanical solution for a particle with rest m_0 if one assumes $p=Ev$. In such a case one may use the special relativistic result $EE = pp + m_0m_0$ and establish the Klein-Gordon equation. A third solution pertains to objects with zero rest mass. As argued in Part I, these do not follow $p=E(v)v$, but rather the classical wave result: $v=E/p$.

In this note we examine massless particles, namely waves on a string, photons and sound, in more detail. For the zero mass case, $dA=0$ so there is motion in such a way as to keep A constant. If one considers periodic motion and uses ((1a)) and ((1b)), a solution which is real and periodic is:

$$d/dt \cos(A) = -v d/dx \cos(A) \quad ((2))$$

A second order partial differential equation is needed as one insists the solution be real. This differs from the quantum mechanical solution of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which is complex for a reason. The modulus must be linked to a probability of 1 for a free particle. The zero mass solution is one of a smeared-out physical wave.

We note that ((1a)) and ((1b)) deal strictly with E energy and p momentum, but $\cos(A)=\cos(-Et+px)$ is associated with a period proportional to $1/E$ and a wavelength proportional to $1/p$. This raises two questions. First, what physical entity is periodic? Secondly, how does the energy appear in the problem as energy and not just 2π frequency of the physical entity? We try to consider this issue for a wave on a string, photon and sound wave.

Flux/Flow

In a number of previous notes, we have argued that for a free particle:

$$d/dx$$
 (partial) $A(x,t) = p$ ((1a)) and d/dt (partial) $A(x,t) = -E$ ((1b))

which have a number of solutions. In these equations one writes $v=x/t$, takes partial derivatives and then sets $x/t=v$ again. We have argued that $A(x,t)=t L(v)$ i.e. the classical action with $L(v)$ being either the relativistic or nonrelativistic Lagrangian ($-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$ or $.5mvv$). Furthermore we have used the form $p=E(v)v$ together with ((1a)) and ((1b)) to derive the form of special relativity $E=m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$). This applies to a particle with rest mass.

It seems ((1a)) and ((1b)) may be extended to describe periodic motion of a physical entity while still being linked to energy E and momentum p. For example, one may write ((1a)) and ((1b)) as eigenvalue equations:

$$-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad ((2b))$$

These are quantum mechanical results for a free particle without any assumption of a rest mass. The modulus is 1 so it is as if one has a kind of two dimensional probability in $\exp(iA)$. If one links these results to a particle with a mass i.e. uses $E = pc + m_0c^2$, one may create the Klein-Gordon quantum mechanical equation from which one may obtain the Schrodinger equation.

A third solution involves periodic motion that is real and applies to a physical entity and not probability. In such a case, one may consider:

$$dA = 0 = -E dt + p dx \quad ((3)) \quad \text{or} \quad v(\text{velocity}) = E/p \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is very different from $p = E(v)/v$ which applies to a particle with rest mass m_0 . To create a periodic equation, the first order partial differential equation will not work-one needs a second order one:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \cos(A) = v^2 \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \cos(A) \quad \text{where} \quad \cos(A) = \cos(-Et + px) \quad ((5))$$

This is a third solution to ((1a)) and ((1b)), but two questions immediately arise. First, what physical entity (which is real i.e. $\cos(A)$) is periodic? Secondly, E and p are related to period and wavelength of the changes in the physical entity, but how are they linked to physical energy and momentum? We examine three examples: a wave on a string, photons and sound to analyze these ideas.

Wave on a String

A wave on a string may be analyzed using Newton's laws applied to tension in a plucked string which is fastened at each end. From this one may obtain a wave equation i.e. ((5)) without use of ((1a)) and ((1b)). In this note, however, we argue that ((1a)) and ((1b)) describe the essence of a number of interrelated problems.

In the case of the string, the physical entity which is periodic is $y(x,t)$ the height of the string above the horizontal. This is a real value and so may be described by $\cos(A)$. Thus the first question is answered, but the second is not. To examine the second, we use the idea of kinetic energy of each segment of the string as given in (1);

$$dKE = \frac{1}{2} u dx \omega^2 \cos(kx) \cos(kx) \quad ((6))$$

where $u = \text{mass/length}$, ω is $2\pi \times \text{frequency}$ and $k = 2\pi/\text{wavelength}$ and A the amplitude

To find the total kinetic energy, one integrates ((6)) over dx and finds:

KE proportional to $\omega^2 k$ ((7))

If one wishes KE (kinetic energy) to be proportional to total energy E (where $\omega = 2\pi E$) then:

$\omega k = \text{constant}$ ((8)) In this case, the constant is velocity which is related to tension and mass/length.

Thus,

KE is proportional to ω ((8))

In other words, E is both a frequency for $y(x,t)$, but is still linked to energy i.e. the kinetic energy of the moving string pieces. (In (1) potential energy is also considered and modeled as that of an oscillator giving a result PE proportional to $\omega^2 k$ as well.)

As a result, this problem makes use of ((1a)) and ((1b)) in two ways. First there is a massless entity, the wave, in the string which follows $v = \omega/k$ or $v = E/p$. This massless wave is synonymous with kinetic and potential energy of mass pieces of the string and one has ((1a)) and ((1b)) with $p = E(v)$ for these pieces. Note $v = \text{constant}$ for the wave is completely different from $v(x,t)$ of the pieces of string. The two energies must be the same. Thus E is proportional to physical energy of the pieces of string (note amplitude also enters the result), but at the same time describes the frequency of the massless string wave.

Photon

For a photon which follows from Maxwell's equations one has a similar scenario. One may again ask what physical entity is periodic. In this case it is the electric field E and the magnetic one B. Thus, E and p are related to period and wavelength for E and B, and there should be a wave equation. This wave equation follows from Maxwell's em equations, but is also a related solution of ((1a)) and ((1b)). The second question is how does E appear as energy? Maxwell's em equations yields:

$\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 B^2 = \text{energy density}$ ((9))

Thus, one has the idea of $\cos(A)\cos(A)$ again just as in the string case and an average value within one wavelength yields ω as the energy of the photon. Thus E is both energy and frequency of a different physical entity namely the electric field and also the magnetic. Again $c = \omega/k$.

Sound

It is possible to obtain a wave equation ((5)) for spatial density from conservation equations associated with Boltzmann's transport equation (2). In such a case, the spatial density or pressure if one uses the ideal gas law $PV=nRT$ (T =temperature, P pressure, V volume, n number of particles and R is a constant) is the physical entity which behaves as $\cos(A)$. Note in quantum mechanics physical density is $W^*(x)W(x)$ so there is a difference.

There seems to be a wave which passes through a medium with mass. This appears to be very similar to the string wave. Using (2) and $\text{pressure}=p = \sin(A)$ one finds:

$$\text{intensity} = \text{pressure} * \text{velocity} = \beta k s_{\max} \sin(A) s_{\max} w \sin(A) \quad ((10))$$

Where β is the bulk modulus $p(x,t)/(dV/V)$ (treated as a constant) and s_{\max} is maximum amplitude. Thus:

$$\text{Intensity integrated over a period } 6.28/w \text{ is proportional to } kw (.5*6.28/w) \quad ((11))$$

Using $v=w/k$ then gives total intensity proportional to $w=6.28 E$. Thus there is not only a frequency related to E , but an energy (part of intensity) which is also linked to E .

Usually an average is created by dividing ((11)) by $6.28/w$. In such a case intensity is proportional to kw or using $v=\text{constant} = w/k$ gives:

$$\text{Intensity average proportional to } ww. \quad ((12))$$

Here EE comes into the final picture, but this pertains to the average intensity of sound.

Question of Negative Values of $\cos(-Et+kx)$

The solution $\cos(-Et+kx)$, although being real, may take on positive and negative values. Given that it applies to a physical entity one needs to interpret what negative and positive values mean. In the case of sound, we argue that $\cos(-Et+kx)$ corresponds to spatial density which cannot be negative overall. The effect of a massless wave, however, may increase density from the unperturbed value in certain regions and decrease it in others. Thus a negative $\cos(-Et+kx)$ value means density has been lowered from the unperturbed value. A similar result holds for the wave on a string. Pieces of the string may be above or below the unperturbed state which is a horizontal line. Similarly, the electric field of the photon may point in one direction or another. Thus it seems that there is no problem with the interpretation of negative values of $\cos(-Et+kx)$.

The Photon as a Quantum Object

The wave equation for massless particles seems to provide an average picture at least for the photon. The wave solution represents a physical wave with energy smeared out over space, but according to Einstein's photoelectric theory, the photon acts as a point particle when it

interacts. It seems this must be kept in mind when dealing with this third solution $dA=0$ of ((1a)) and ((1b))

$v=E/p$ and E as Energy

It is interesting to note that in the examples above one starts with a physical entity described by the real function $\cos(-Et+px)$. In other words E plays the role of a frequency and not an energy. To see how E acts as energy, one needs to calculate an energy or energy related quantity in the problem. In the above examples this led to results involving $\cos(-Et+px)\cos(-Et+px)$ in all three cases as well as various factors of k and w. After performing an integral over space or time (and possibly averaging), the expression w/k appears at least for the case of a wave on a string or a photon. This leads one to conclude that $w/k=\text{constant}$ if one wishes to have $w=6.28E$. (The constant turns out to represent the constant velocity of the wave with zero rest mass.) Thus the relationship $v=w/k$ seems to be directly linked to E appearing as an energy in an energy or energy related calculation which brings a new physical entity into the picture ($y(x,t)$ for a string, electric and magnetic fields for a photon, density for a phonon) which is periodic in time in this same energy E.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the flow/flux equations for a free particle d/dx (partial) $A(x,t) = p$ and d/dt (partial) $A(x,t) = -E$ which have a solution $A = -Et+px$ may be associated with different types of physical solutions. In particular, if $p=E(v)v$ one describes a particle with rest mass in a special relativistic scenario. Creating an eigenvalue equation $-id/dx \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and $id/dt \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$ and linking it to the special relativistic results $EE = pp + m_0m_0$ one obtains the Klein Gordon equation of quantum mechanics (for a particle with rest mass m_0).

In this note, we argue that there is a third solution, namely enforcing $dA=0 = -Edt + px$. This leads to $v=E/p$ which is very different from $p=E(v)v$ and does not describe a particle with rest mass. In other words, it describes one with zero rest mass. $dA=0$ is equivalent (using ((1a)) and ((1b))) to the classical wave equation: $d/dt d/dt \cos(A) = vvd/dx d/dx \cos(A)$.

In this note we ask what real valued physical entity is periodic and secondly, given that E acts like a frequency, how does it also behave as an energy? We consider three examples, a wave on a string, a photon and a phonon. In all three cases there are entities which behave as $\cos(A)$ namely, the height of the string above the horizontal, the electric and magnetic fields in the photon and finally spatial density or pressure ($PV=nRT$) in the phonon. In all three cases, E is not simply linked to the frequency of this physical entity, but behaves as an energy. This result is linked with $v=E/p$ where v is constant velocity which differs from $p=E(v)v$ for a particle with rest mass.

For the case of a wave in a string, the kinetic energy of the string pieces ($y(x,t)y(x,t)$ ultimately integrated over dx) are proportional to E (as is the integrated potential energy. For a photon, energy density= $aEIEI + bBB$ where EI is the electric field and B the magnetic so within one wavelength one has average energy of $w=6.28E$. Finally in the case of sound, Intensity

before it is divided by time= $1/E$ is proportional to w . Average intensity becomes proportional to kk or ww i.e. EE , so energy is linked to a quantity (intensity).

References

1.

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